

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B290
 Date: 30 April 2007
 Take Off: 12:54:40 19:12:12
 Landing: 17:39:51 20:10:04
 Flight Time: 4h45m11 0h57m52

Campaign: IASI – METOP and AQUA overpass

Operating Area: Oklahoma ARM site

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Steve Ball	Directflight
3	CCM	Sue Angold	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Stuart Newman	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Ruth Purvis	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics	Paul James	FAAM
7	AVAPS / CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
8	ARIES	Joss Kent	Met Office
9	MARSS / Wet Neph / PSAP	Dave Pollard	Met Office
10	AMS	Will Morgan	University of Manchester
11	CVI / FWVS	Jeff Brown	Met Office
12	Mission Scientist 2	Alessio Bozzo	University of Bologna
14			
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B290
 Date: 2 May 2007
 Project: IASI
 Location: Gulf of Mexico

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
121551		Start-Up	-.10 kft	179	29'36.28N 95'10.06W
124928		ASP	-.11 kft	090	Open
125440		T/O	-.12 kft	178	
133619		Video	23.0 kft	119	UFC1 DFC1
134551	141037	Profile 1	23.0 - -.14 kft	119	q1021
135417		PSAP	14.4 kft	119	Filter change
141616	144121	Run 1	-.09 - -.10 kft	033	100' A to B
144121	144656	Profile 2	0.50 - 4.8 kft	039	
144340		comment	1.1 kft	032	1000' min adjust
144947	151020	Profile 2.2	4.9 - 28.0 kft	216	start 5000'
150026			17.3 kft	218	DLU reset as lost data
150251		PSAP	20.3 kft	220	Filter change
151025	151404	Run 2	28.0 kft	222	
151618		Video	28.0 kft	194	DFC 2 UFC2
151819	154503	Run 2.2	28.0 kft	029	A to B
151900		Sonde 1	28.0 kft	024	
152201		Sonde 2	28.0 kft	028	
152500		Sonde 3	28.0 kft	032	
152700		Sonde 4	28.0 kft	031	
152903		Overpass	28.0 kft	031	METOP 1529Z
153200		Sonde 5	28.0 kft	031	
153700		Sonde 6	28.0 kft	032	
154858	161700	Run 2.3	28.0 kft	211	B to A
154924		Sonde 7	28.0 kft	204	
155400		Sonde 8	28.0 kft	220	
155900		Sonde 9	28.0 kft	221	
160359		Sonde 10	28.0 kft	222	
160900		Sonde 11	28.0 kft	221	
161358		Sonde 12	28.0 kft	220	
161705	162501	Orbit	28.0 kft	220	15 to 25 degrees
163122	165424	Profile 3	28.0 - -.16 kft	359	A to C
164532		Video	9.8 kft	359	UFC3 DFC3
165424	170528	Profile 4	-.16 - 11.8 kft	358	500ft min at 1000'
165507		rate	0.27 kft	358	1000ft /min
170903	170941	Run 3	11.8 kft	320	
170957	171850	Run 3	11.8 kft	280	
171019			11.8 kft	272	change of heading 270
171850	172019	Profile 5	11.8 - 10.8 kft	306	
172019	172914	Run 4	10.8 kft	306	\
173951		Land	-.16 kft	016	
174345		ASP	-.15 kft	342	shut
174701		New Orleans	-.15 kft	103	29'59.80N 90'15.75W
190513		ASP	-.13 kft	000	
191212		T/O	-.15 kft	000	
201004		Land	-.04 kft	000	Ellington
201328		ASP	-.02 kft	000	closed
201542		Shutdown	-.02 kft	000	29'36.23N 95'10.06W

B290 Track 30-APR-07

Sortie Brief Gulf of Mexico

Flight B290

Monday 30 April 2007

Mission Scientist: Stuart Newman

Briefing: 0530L = 1030Z

Take off: 0730L = 1230Z

Landing: approx. 1240L New Orleans, 1500L Ellington

Satellite overpass: 1529Z

Aim: To underfly IASI on the Metop satellite in the Gulf of Mexico for satellite validation and retrieval studies

Location: Eastern Gulf of Mexico

Weather conditions: Clear skies or broken cloud

Key instruments: ARIES, MARSS, SWS, AVAPS, Core Chem, Cloud Phys

Fixed Points: BAe 146 to follow fixed ground positions as follows:

Over Gulf of Mexico

Fixed point A: (26°20' N, 88°30' W)

Fixed point B: (28°20' N, 86°50' W)

Fixed point C: (29°00' N, 88°30' W)

1. Take off from Houston and transit to point A, profiling down to arrive at low level (50 ft) (85 mins)
2. Straight and level run (SLR) from A to B at 100ft (50 mins)
3. Profile from B climbing from 100 ft to FL300 to arrive at A (35 mins)
4. SLR from A to B at FL300 (30 mins) – **Overpass** occurs at FL300 at **1529Z**
5. SLR from B to A at FL300 (30 mins)
6. Profile descent from B out of area towards point C (35 mins)
7. Recovery to New Orleans for refuel (35 mins; total time 310 mins)
8. Refuel (80 mins)
9. Transit to Ellington (60 mins)

Dropsondes:

Key dropsonde release times relative to satellite overpass are, as nearly as possible:

T-10 1519

T-7 1522

T-4 1525

T-2 1527

Otherwise aim to release sondes at intervals of approx. 5 minutes, or about six per run at high level.

Mission scientist's debrief for JAIVEx flight B290 on 30 April 2007

S. M. Newman

Summary:

Good clear sky satellite validation case only slightly complicated by occasional cloud.
Excellent flight for FWVS versus General Eastern hygrometer.
Good correlations between aerosol sampling instruments.

The aim of the sortie was to underfly IASI on the MetOp satellite, launching sondes and carrying out radiometric measurements for validation purposes. The flight was conducted over the Gulf of Mexico east of New Orleans with the sub-satellite track slightly further east still. A delay in acceptance of the flight plan meant a delayed take off, resulting in changes to the sortie. A profile descent into the area of operations (very good comparison between FWVS and General Eastern, with the former avoiding the latter's over-compensatory oscillations) was followed by a truncated run at 100 feet to characterise the surface with ARIES and other radiometers. SWS recorded a series of angles for solar reflectance studies. A ship plume was sampled during this run with good correlations between AMS, PCASP, ozone and nephelometer time series. A profile ascent to FL280 revealed enhanced CO concentrations compared with earlier in the sortie.

The high level runs commenced in time for dropping sondes in conjunction with the satellite overpass, and a total of twelve were released. The southern end of the run exhibited generally good clear conditions, with marine cumulus and patchy overhead cirrus along the run. The high level runs terminated with two orbits at 15° and 25° for Alessio Bozzo's sea surface reflection work.

The final descent out of the area was away from the overpass run towards New Orleans to the north, followed by ascent from 50 feet in the same directions. A marked step-change in aerosol properties was seen at around 6000 feet on descent and ascent.

The flight should prove to be valuable for IASI cal/val studies in near-clear sky conditions.

Mission scientist Debrief Summary

29th April 2007

JAIVEx Gulf of Mexico during MetOp and AQUA

Mission Scientist: Clare Lee

Weather Conditions:

For the majority of the science there was low level Cu or StCu, with clear skies above. Small quantities of cirrus observed on occasion in the area. Through the flight the atmosphere dried, with drier levels in the South than the North.

In the moister areas the aircraft produced intermittent contrails (not recorded on the cameras, as UFC and DFC were recorded for some of the flight).

Sortie:

This flight was coincident with 2 satellite overpasses and the WB57 aircraft (with NASI-I and S-HIS onboard). To sample close to the satellite times, 21 sondes were launched.

Instrument Issues:

SWS: All OK

ARIES: All OK

MARSS: OK, except ch16

AVAPS: Some intermittent signal problems

Core: OK

Aircraft Scientist's Log

MISSION SCIENTIST: STUART NEWMAN

JAIVEX GULF OF MEXICO

Flight No **B.290**.....

Date **30/4/07**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
¹²⁵⁴ 125440	TAKE-OFF				Delayed T/O due to filing of flight plan T/O 2000 ↓ 100 PCASP
1333	Transit	FL230	119	27°54' 91.2°E	Largely clear below, some high cloud + haze; T -20.8 Td -47.3 Wind 6ms ¹ /287° MARSS+ARIES report variability above in radiometric measurements
1342	Transit	FL230	119	27°30' 90.6°E	Looks clear above + below, but Ci visible around us; T -20.6, Td -47.9 W. 6ms ¹ 280°
134551	P1	FL230 ↓	119	27°18' 90.24'	Clear sky column * GOOD PROFILE FOR FWUS * ↓ following GE but without oscillations
1401	"	3000'	121	26°42' 89.12'	Dew pt depression 27°C, large! Very dry layer
1406	"	3800'	121	26°30' 89.0'	Calm sea state (5ms ⁻¹ / 60° wind) CO profile grad. incr. 120 ↑ 150 ppb
141037	end P1	50 ft	119	26°24' 88.42'	Pretty smooth sea surface, no white
14145				26°18' 88.5'	Brief climb from 100' to turn for run
141616	R1	100 ft	034	26°18' 88.26'	T 23.3°C, Td 19.6 Profile PCASP ↑ at 8000' peak 100' 3000 cc ⁻¹ down from 200-400 cc at high level
1420					Sea scattering: calm surface ⇒
141945					PCASP 1500 above background when passing over ship wake just behind the ship passing to S' board (2300 cc)
1424					More scattering at sea surface? more water glint ARIES reports clear above
1428	R1	100 ft	033	26°54' 88.0'	O ₃ ↑ PCASP ↑ AMS ↑ neph ↑ 80 ppb 1600 cc during run ↓ from 1200

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.290**

 Date **30/4/07**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1430	R1	100'	036	26°54' 87°14'	Some wisps high level cloud?
1432					CO 194 O3 82.7 ppb
1434			036	27°6' 87°14'	Cu off to s' board horizon, possibly Ci above
1436					MASS reports more upper level moisture assoc. high cirrus?
1437					CO 203 ppb O3 82
143930	(R1)	100'	035	27°24' 87°30'	25°C Heilmann Temp.
14421	end R1 P2.1	100' ↑	035	27°24' 87°30'	More Cu closer to s' board, definitely some high cirrus, more obvious here
1445					SWS has been recording series of angles for solar reflection at 100'
144656	Interr.	5000'		27°42' 87°18'	CO 207.9, O3 66.5 much higher on ascent than descent
144947	Recommence P2.1				PCASP drop off 1-2,000 ft b'ground 4,000 2100 ↓ 400 at 3,500 ft
1452	" P2.1	8600'	218	27°36' 87°24'	Cu below off to port (coming below us)
1509	"	27800'	222	26°30' 88°12'	Looks clear above + below
151020	end P				
151025	R2.1	FL2800	222		Short run for positioning, Ci ahead
151404	end R2.1	"			RD-93 senses to go
1517				26°12' 88°30'	Pretty clear above, occasional wisps Ci
1518	R2.2	FL280	027		Sonde #1 151900
1520				26°18' 88°24'	Cu cloud sheet ahead/below / to starboard; looks clear above here Southern end good clear
					Sonde #2 152201
152431	(R2.2)	FL280		26°42' 88°6'	T-33.3 Td -41.4
					Sonde #3 152500 AIRS: Ci above

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.290**

 Date **30/4/07**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
152650	(R2.2)	FL280	031	26°34'88"0	Approaching Cu street below ↑ 146
					Sonde #4 152700
					off #1 641 m
					#2 2540 m
					#3 5105 m
					#4 6897 m
152940					Ahead cloud street now, we are clipping w/ edge of it
153120					SWS picks up cloud
					Sonde #5 153200 21-15,000ft sonde signal problems with dropouts
1535	(R2.2)	FL280	033	27°30'87"24	Approaching Ci up ahead
					T = -33.6, Td -51.9 Wind 10ms / 318°
					Sonde #6 153700
1545	end R2.2	FL280		28°12'86"54	Pretty clear above + below
154858	R2.3	FL280	209	28°12'86"54	High level cloud above
					Sonde #7 154903
155347		FL280	219	27°54'87"6	Ci overhead now, wispy
					Sonde #8 155400
1555				27°42'87"8	ARIES "clear above" although Ci by eye
					Sonde #9 155900
1602					ARIES "variability aims" ↑ 146
1603					Passing over Cu field: below
					Sonde #10 160359
1605	(R2.3)	FL280	221	27°0'87"54	Fairly clear above + below here

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.290**.....
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 Date **30/4/07**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
160815	R2.3	FL280	220	26°48', 88°0'	Looks v. clear above + below here
					Sonde # 11 1608 160900
					Sonde # 12 161358
161440					MASS "moister down below"
161700	end R2.3	FL280			
161705	01	"		26°48', 88°30'	L. Orbit with radiometers at nadir for sea surface reflection studies [150] At this bank angle some data is lost from highest sonde (#12)
162105	(01)	FL280			Half way round orbit, locally clear above + below but some high clouds in vicinity
162501	01				Tighter turn at 25° bank angle for better scattering angle coverage
	02	FL280		26°12', 88°12'	Still locally clear above + below
162826	end 02	"			
163122	P3	FL280 ↓	355	26°24', 88°24'	low CO at start descent (123.3 ppb)
164130	"	FL154	357	27°12', 88°24'	FWVS continues to perform v. well cf GE (Structure better than GE fluctuations)
16445					T _d : moist at high level, drying below
164530	(P3)	FL100	358	27°30', 88°24'	T = 7.6°C, T _d ≈ 27.9°C
164744		7000'			35°C dew pt depression
164920		5000'			Over Cu just below, aerosol count ↑ PCASP 2000 counts 5600 ft step change
1652		1300'		27°54', 88°24'	Bottoming out heading North away from previous turns, towards New Orleans
165424	end P3 start P4	50'			
1656					Rate of ascent increased due to helicopter ahead + below
1700		6500'			Marked haze below; dip 5800 ft again, step change

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B290

Date: 30/04/07	Operator: JT	DRS Time: +0	AU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 1
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
125440	2000	0.06	2	8	1	0	0	0	0						0	Take off	
130500	1300	0.06	2	8	1	0	0	0	0						0	Boundary layer	
130300	900	0.06	2	8	1	0	0	0	0						0	Strange oscillation in PCASP conc 13:03-05	
131040	480	0.06	2	0	0	0	0	0	0						0	2dp rearmed 20Kft	
134551	394	0.06	3	0	0	0	0	0	0						0	Start P1 23kft	
140000	537	0.06	4	8	1	0	0	0	0						0	8ft 2dp rearmed	
140411	1328	0.09	4	8	1	0	0	0	0						0	5kft (rise started 140000)	
140530	1395	0.09	4	8	1	0	0	0	0						0	4	
140637	1641	0.09	4	8	1	0	0	0	0						0	3	
140748	2480	0.08	4	8	1	0	0	0	0						0	2	
140849	2024	0.08	4	8	1	0	0	0	0						0	1 conc oscilated on P max 3000140900 800ft	
141036	1833	0.08	4	8	1	0	0	0	0						0	50ft End P1	
141614	1424	0.08	4	8	1	0	0	0	0						0	Run 1	
142000	1231	0.08	4	8	1	0	0	0	0						0	141945 PCASP peak ship plume (2300)	
142610	1466	0.08	4	8	1	0	0	0	0						0		
142850	1648	0.08	4	8	1	0	0	0	0						0	Ramping up as of 1427ish	
143200	2115	0.08	4	10	1	0	0	0	0						0		
143600	1977	0.08	4	4	1	0	0	0	0						0		
144122	2049	0.08	4	6	1	0	0	0	0						0	End of run 1 Start P2	
144321	2089	0.08	4	6	1	0	0	0	0						0	1kft	
144432	826	0.08	5	6	1	0	0	0	0						0	2 drop off starts at 144340	
144526	590	0.08	5	3	1	0	0	0	0						0	3 kft	
144623	523	0.08	5	1	1	0	0	0	0						0	4kft	
144656	498	0.08	5	8	1	0	0	0	0						0	5 kft PCASP oscilating again 145100 on	
145421	500	0.08	5	8	1	0	0	0	0						0	10 kft	
150000	500		5	10		0	0	0	0						0	19kft	
150704	359	0.06	5	0	0	0	0	0	0						0	25 kft	
151020	400	0.06	5	0	0	0	0	0	0						0	28 kft end P2	
								NOISE									
163122	500	0.06	7	0	0	0	0	0	0						0	P3 28kft	
164522	464	0.06	7	3	1	0	0	NOISE								10kft 2dp rearmed	
164820	1924	0.09	7	10	1	0	0								0	5.6kft very disticnt boundary	
164950	2000	0.09	7	10	1	0	0								0	4	
165127	1744	0.08	7	8	1	0	0								0	2	
165218	2126	0.08	7	5	1	0	0								0	1	
165424	2409	0.08	8	3	1	0	0								0	50ft end P3 start P4	
165540	1744	0.08	8	3	1	0	0									1kft	
165618	1486	0.08	8	3	1	0	0									2	
165720	1537	0.08	8	8	1	0	0									3	
165821	1093	0.09	8	8	1	0	0									4	
165915	738	0.09	8	8	1	0	0									5	
170000	230	0.09	8	8	1	0	0									5.8	
170351	278	0.06	8	1	1	0	0									10 kft	
170528	291	0.06	8	10	1	0	0									12 kft end of P4vf23	
172228																2dp rearmed	

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B290 **T/O:** 125440
Date of flight: 30/04/07 **Land:** 173951

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt	NO	hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B290 **T/O:** 125440
Date of flight: 30/04/07 **Land:** 173951

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	Yes	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	Yes	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	Yes	
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	Yes	Size of Bnnn.dat = 194352
6) FLOODS> WAVE WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Blocks read =56040 Blocks written = 56040 Bad reads = 0
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i> f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i> g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	yes	Start = 125440 End = 174000 Ignore error message scroll (vestigial error from tapes) Are FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC files in PMSDATA? Are they non-zero in size?
8) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> imagedisplay a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Time from IWC plot: N d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP e) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i> f) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i> g) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images) ii). WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i> e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i> f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10 iii). WAVE> exit to create files iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of	NO CLOUD	2D image display and printing Must be done from FLOODS itself. Note any problems with images Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again Start = End = FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps Notes on this in instructions

CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		
9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D		NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful. X = Start = End = Time data processed to = 2dproc files present? *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat
10) FLOODS> WAVE i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Error message about HDDR file should be ignored. Records =
11) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default		X = Y = (X+1)
12) CHECKS: Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i>		Correlated?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B290 **T/O:** 125440
Date of flight: 30/04/07 **Land:** 173951

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:		
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. 1.8ccs⁻¹</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Min size = Vol flow rate =
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		X = Y = X+1 =
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and NEPH peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph total blue scatter</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>		Merged OK?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B290a **T/O:** 191212
Date of flight: 30/04/07 **Land:** 201004

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt	NO	hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B290a **T/O:** 191212
Date of flight: 30/04/07 **Land:** 201004

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	Yes	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	Yes	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	Yes	
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	Yes	Size of Bnnn.dat = 194352
6) FLOODS> WAVE WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Blocks read = 10701 Blocks written = 10701 Bad reads = 0
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i> f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i> g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	yes	Start = 191200 End = 211100 Ignore error message scroll (vestigial error from tapes) FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA, SEC in PMSDATA
8) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> imagedisplay a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Time from IWC plot: N d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP e) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i> f) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i> g) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images) ii). WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i> e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i> f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10 iii). WAVE> exit to create files iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files	NO CLOUD	2D image display and printing Must be done from FLOODS itself. Note any problems with images Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again Start = End = FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps Notes on this in instructions

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>		<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X =</p> <p>Start = End =</p> <p>Time data processed to =</p> <p>2dproc files present? *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>		<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored.</p> <p>Records =</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>		<p>X = Y = (X+1)</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>		<p>Correlated?</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B290a **T/O:** 191212
Date of flight: 30/04/07 **Land:** 201004

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Yes	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. 1.8ccs⁻¹</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>	YES	Min size = 2, Vol flow rate = 0.8
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit	Yes	Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>	yes	MFDB - MFDC Y = X+1 =
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and NEPH peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph total blue scatter</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>		Merged OK?

FAAM Dropsonde Flight Log

Flight No.	B290	Date	30 Apr 2007
Page No.	1 of 2	Operator	Doug Anderson

GMT	Sonde No.	Event	Comments
		<i>e.g. launch, splashdown</i>	<i>e.g. wind data? PTH data? Lat/Long NB strings of dropsonde data contain: time, pressure hPa, T deg C, RH %, wind direction deg, wind speed m/s, longitude, latitude, height m</i>
15:19:03	1	Launch	328.90 -33.40 47.85 269.00 17.40 -16.90 -88.488300 26.300900 8543.20
15:29:54	1	splashdown	1019.10 23.46 76.31 37.06 1.56 -9.79 -88.467915 26.271563 99999.00 gps dropout between 21000' and approx 15000'
15:22:06	2	Launch	329.00 -33.50 54.17 277.10 16.90 -16.80 -88.314100 26.543600 8540.50
15:32:32	2	splashdown	1019.35 23.78 75.79 351.13 1.75 -11.73 -88.296925 26.510638 99999.00 same GPS dropouts between 21000' and 15000' approx
15:25:03	3	Launch	329.20 -33.40 40.42 288.60 12.80 -17.30 -88.142700 26.768600 8536.80
15:35:50	3	splashdown	1020.10 24.12 76.56 337.96 2.30 -11.10 -88.125678 26.737900 99999.00 Same GPS dropouts between 21000' and approx 15000'
15:27:03	4	Launch	328.90 -33.80 51.87 299.90 13.40 -17.60 -88.023300 26.915500 8541.70
15:37:42	4	splashdown	1020.37 24.38 68.23 13.15 2.05 -11.76 -88.007665 26.884874 99999.00 usual GPS dropouts for today between 21000' and 15000' approx
15:32:03	5	Launch	328.80 -33.70 28.19 313.90 14.10 -17.60 -87.726300 27.273800 8544.20
15:42:38	5	splashdown	1020.34 24.73 69.70 38.25 6.24 -0.48 -87.713372 27.245749 99999.00 GPS dropouts between 21000' and 15000'
15:37:03	6	Launch	329.00 -33.60 14.79 317.40 10.50 -17.70 -87.429500 27.629200 8540.40
15:48:04	6	splashdown	1019.72 24.73 68.14 8.77 3.15 -10.64 -87.417774 27.600421 99999.00 GPS dropouts as usual between 21000 and 15000 and also lower
15:49:15	7	Launch	328.90 -34.80 56.05 310.80 10.20 -17.40 -86.916300 28.285100 8542.90
15:59:32	7	splashdown	1020.39 24.32 73.25 0.13 5.21 -9.06 -86.896559 28.271896 99999. GPS dropouts from around 22000' to 15000'ish
15:54:03	8	Launch	329.20 -34.40 51.68 300.90 9.50 -17.00 -87.169900 27.939000 8536.80
16:04:38	8	splashdown	1019.94 24.50 70.16 25.12 3.83 -10.60 -87.156825 27.913326 99999. GPS dropouts between 22000' and 16000'ish
15:59:03	9	Launch	329.00 -33.80 15.08 292.30 12.90 -16.40 -87.463600 27.588300 8540.50
16:09:55	9	splashdown	1019.77 24.64 65.84 14.23 4.04 -11.62 -87.450639 27.562942 99999.00
16:04:03	10	Launch	328.90 -33.70 26.97 283.00 17.80 -16.00 -87.760400 27.232400 8541.70
16:14:33	10	splashdown	1019.68 24.61 71.64 29.38 3.73 -11.44 -87.744523 27.207786 99999.00

Flight No.	B290	Date	30 Apr 2007
Page No.	2 of 2	Operator	Doug Anderson

GMT	Sonde No.	Event	Comments
		<i>e.g. launch, splashdown</i>	<i>e.g. wind data? PTH data? Lat/Long NB strings of dropsonde data contain: time, pressure hPa, T deg C, RH %, wind direction deg, wind speed m/s, longitude, latitude, height m</i>
16:09:03	11	Launch	328.90 -33.70 40.74 268.40 17.20 -16.10 -88.054600 26.876700 8542.90
16:19:45	11	splashdown	1019.47 24.19 70.67 36.63 3.19 -6.76 -88.038182 26.848113 99999.00 some loss of GPS during orbit (last three mins or so of drop)
16:14:00	12	Launch	328.90 -33.40 42.17 264.70 19.90 -15.90 -88.338300 26.530800 8542.30
16:24:45	12	splashdown	1019.50 23.96 71.92 19.67 2.12 -10.79 -88.319416 26.502046 99999.00 partial Loss of GPS signal during orbit, worse at start, for last two thirds of drop

B290 CVI log

4/30/07	1:33:37 PM	133300	zeroed lyman and adjusted pcasp flow
4/30/07	1:57:01 PM	135600	zeroed lyman and adjusted pcasp flow
4/30/07	2:47:35 PM	144721	zeroed lyman and adjusted pcasp flow
4/30/07	2:50:52 PM	1450381	adjusted pcasp flow

B290_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog_BAK1

```

11:00:59.20 --- - - - -
11:00:59.20 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
11:00:59.20 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
                        tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
11:00:59.20 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B290
11:00:59.20 --- - - - -
11:01:31.57 SWS - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
11:01:37.50 USH - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
11:01:43.39 LSH - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
11:01:53.58 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
11:01:58.16 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
11:02:04.14 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
11:02:07.98 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
11:02:36.09 SWS - - - 750 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 750ms.
11:02:41.02 SWS - - - 750 - NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 750ms.
11:02:44.92 USH - - - 990 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 990ms.
11:02:50.57 USH - - - 990 - NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 990ms.
11:02:56.45 LSH - - - 990 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 990ms.
11:03:01.83 LSH - - - 990 - NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 990ms.
11:03:12.92 LSH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:03:12.92 USH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:03:12.92 SWS - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:03:24.52 LSH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:03:24.78 USH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:03:24.87 SWS - - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:03:32.86 SWS - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:03:34.80 LSH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:03:35.06 USH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:03:52.67 --- - - - - *** no problems on start up
13:00:48.21 USH - - - 500 - VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 500ms.
13:00:53.68 LSH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:00:53.89 SWS - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:00:54.54 USH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:01:01.82 SWS - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:01:04.02 LSH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:01:04.94 USH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:08:10.73 USH - - - 350 - VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 350ms.
13:08:14.90 USH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:08:25.19 USH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:09:04.39 SWS - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:09:04.54 LSH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:09:04.89 USH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:09:12.33 SWS - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:09:14.94 LSH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:09:15.23 USH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:10:04.95 USH - - - 300 - VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.
13:10:08.34 USH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:10:18.68 USH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:14:17.93 USH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:14:18.02 LSH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:14:18.11 SWS - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:14:26.30 SWS - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:14:28.49 LSH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:14:29.32 USH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:14:30.53 USH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:22:21.40 SWS - - - 500 - VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
13:22:27.42 LSH - - - 750 - VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 750ms.
13:22:36.32 LSH - - - 500 - VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
13:22:39.84 LSH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:22:40.18 SWS - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:22:40.37 USH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:22:48.12 SWS - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:22:50.21 LSH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:22:50.73 USH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:32:07.91 USH - - - 250 - VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
13:32:12.32 USH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:32:12.59 LSH - - - - - Dark measurement started.

```

13:32:12.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:32:20.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:32:22.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:32:22.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:43:02.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:43:03.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:43:03.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:43:10.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:43:13.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:43:13.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:46:06.13	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile descent
13:46:52.72	USH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
13:46:55.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:47:05.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:48:37.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:48:38.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:48:38.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:48:46.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:48:48.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:48:48.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:49:51.98	LSH	-	-	990	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 990ms.
13:49:58.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:50:08.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:56:39.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:56:39.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:56:39.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:56:47.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:56:49.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:56:50.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:02:14.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:14.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:15.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:22.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:02:24.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:02:25.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:03:10.32	SWS	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
14:03:28.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:03:36.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:04:25.16	USH	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 990ms to 750ms.
14:04:27.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:04:35.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:06:45.11	---	-	-	-	-	*** sh will indicate "sws head" during the next run
14:07:29.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:07:29.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:07:30.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:07:37.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:07:38.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:07:40.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:11:46.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** 100ft for start of run
14:13:14.92	---	-	-	-	-	*** sh to 114aft
14:13:31.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:13:31.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:13:31.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:13:39.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:13:39.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:13:42.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:15:59.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:15:59.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:16:00.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:16:07.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:16:07.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:16:10.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:16:17.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** start f run
14:18:51.73	---	-	-	-	-	*** sh 144asft
14:18:54.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:18:54.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:18:55.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:03.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

14:19:04.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:19:05.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:19:05.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:19:27.70	USH	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
14:19:30.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:38.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:21:08.71	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
14:21:12.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:21:13.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:21:13.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:21:20.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:21:21.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:21:23.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:39.49	---	-	-	-	-	*** sh 156f
14:23:42.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:23:42.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:23:43.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:23:50.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:51.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:53.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:26:26.08	---	-	-	-	-	*** sh 126f
14:26:31.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:26:31.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:26:31.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:26:38.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:26:39.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:26:41.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:28:52.82	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
14:28:58.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:28:58.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:28:58.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:29:06.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:29:06.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:29:08.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:29:13.57	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 350ms.
14:29:19.86	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 200ms.
14:29:28.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:29:36.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:32:00.21	---	-	-	-	-	*** sh 114 aft
14:32:05.50	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 400ms.
14:32:11.55	SWS	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
14:32:15.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:32:15.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:32:15.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:32:23.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:32:23.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:32:25.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:34:34.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** sh 144 aft
14:34:38.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:34:38.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:34:38.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:34:46.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:34:46.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:34:49.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:36:54.26	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
14:36:58.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:36:58.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:36:58.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:37:06.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:37:06.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:37:09.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:39:18.24	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
14:39:24.49	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 200ms.
14:39:30.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:39:30.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:39:30.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:39:38.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:39:38.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:39:40.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

14:41:23.06	---	-	-	-	*** end of run 1
14:51:03.80	USH	-	-	100	- VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
14:51:09.11	USH	-	-	-	500 NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
14:51:17.96	SWS	-	-	250	- VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 250ms.
14:51:21.68	SWS	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
14:51:21.89	USH	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
14:51:22.05	LSH	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
14:51:27.33	USH	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
14:51:29.62	SWS	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
14:51:33.46	LSH	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
14:51:34.67	LSH	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
15:02:20.78	SWS	174R	-	-	- Telescope position set to 174R
15:02:36.95	---	-	-	-	*** ready for overpass run
15:03:47.17	SWS	-	-	300	- VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 300ms.
15:03:51.33	SWS	-	-	400	- VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 400ms.
15:03:57.04	USH	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
15:03:57.06	SWS	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
15:03:57.40	LSH	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
15:04:02.48	USH	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
15:04:05.19	SWS	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
15:04:07.80	LSH	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
15:10:07.59	LSH	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
15:10:07.79	USH	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
15:10:08.03	SWS	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
15:10:13.25	USH	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
15:10:15.96	SWS	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
15:10:17.97	LSH	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
15:10:46.16	---	-	-	-	*** start of run 2.1
15:12:31.87	LSH	-	-	750	- VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 750ms.
15:12:36.61	LSH	-	-	500	- VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
15:12:42.52	LSH	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
15:12:52.86	LSH	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
15:14:14.07	---	-	-	-	*** end of run
15:15:11.77	USH	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
15:15:11.80	LSH	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
15:15:12.29	SWS	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
15:15:17.20	USH	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
15:15:20.22	SWS	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
15:15:22.31	LSH	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
15:18:28.91	---	-	-	-	*** start of run
15:19:42.50	SWS	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
15:19:42.59	USH	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
15:19:42.82	LSH	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
15:19:48.14	USH	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
15:19:50.44	SWS	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
15:19:53.25	LSH	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
15:24:11.96	SWS	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
15:24:11.98	USH	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
15:24:12.81	LSH	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
15:24:17.60	USH	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
15:24:19.91	SWS	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
15:24:23.14	LSH	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
15:24:31.29	SWS	6F	-	-	- Telescope position set to 6F
15:24:52.20	SWS	-	-	750	- VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
15:24:58.25	SWS	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
15:25:06.19	SWS	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
15:26:18.14	SWS	174R	-	-	- Telescope position set to 174R
15:26:22.13	SWS	-	-	350	- VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 350ms.
15:26:30.13	LSH	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
15:26:30.16	SWS	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
15:26:30.25	USH	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
15:26:35.98	USH	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
15:26:38.27	SWS	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
15:26:40.47	LSH	-	-	-	- Manual scene recording started.
15:29:00.98	---	-	-	-	*** metop overpass
15:31:10.40	SWS	-	-	250	- VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 250ms.
15:31:13.91	SWS	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
15:31:14.04	USH	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.
15:31:14.16	LSH	-	-	-	- Dark measurement started.

15:31:19.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:31:21.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:31:24.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:31:32.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:31:32.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:31:32.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:31:37.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:31:40.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:31:43.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:32:01.60	---	-	-	-	-	*** over 3/8 cu2
15:35:27.26	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
15:35:35.51	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 500ms.
15:35:42.04	SWS	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
15:35:47.34	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
15:35:50.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:35:50.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:35:50.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:35:55.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:35:58.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:36:01.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:36:59.84	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 350ms.
15:37:04.44	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
15:37:06.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:37:07.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:37:07.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:37:12.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:37:15.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:37:17.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:41:50.74	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
15:41:57.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:41:58.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:41:58.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:42:03.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:42:06.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:42:08.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:42:14.31	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 200ms.
15:42:59.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:43:07.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:43:20.59	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
15:43:28.34	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 250ms.
15:43:31.41	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
15:43:36.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:43:36.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:43:36.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:43:41.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:43:44.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:43:46.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:45:08.45	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
15:47:13.56	---	-	-	-	-	*** sh is "sws head" for next run
15:48:44.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:48:44.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:48:44.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:48:49.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:48:52.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:48:55.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:48:57.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 3.2
15:49:26.13	---	-	-	-	-	*** sh 114a
15:52:03.83	---	-	-	-	-	*** sh 144aft
15:52:09.40	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 300ms.
15:52:14.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:52:14.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:52:14.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:52:15.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:52:20.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:52:23.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:52:25.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:53:10.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:55:20.20	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
15:55:22.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

15:55:22.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:22.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:27.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:55:30.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:55:33.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:57:37.74	---	-	-	-	-	*** sh 156 fore
15:57:44.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:57:44.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:57:44.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:57:49.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:57:52.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:57:54.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:59:59.58	---	-	-	-	-	*** sh 126 fore
16:00:21.00	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
16:00:27.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:00:27.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:00:27.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:00:32.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:00:35.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:00:38.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:01:20.50	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
16:01:24.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:01:32.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:02:43.54	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
16:02:53.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:02:53.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:02:53.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:02:58.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:03:01.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:03:03.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:03:08.48	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 350ms.
16:03:14.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:03:21.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:05:46.51	---	-	-	-	-	*** sh 114 aft
16:05:52.85	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 250ms.
16:05:57.68	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
16:06:01.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:06:01.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:06:02.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:06:07.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:06:10.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:06:11.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:06:12.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:08:34.89	---	-	-	-	-	*** sh 126 fore
16:08:40.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:08:40.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:08:41.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:08:46.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:08:48.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:08:51.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:10:58.38	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
16:11:03.02	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 300ms.
16:11:06.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:11:06.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:11:07.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:11:12.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:11:15.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:11:17.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:13:32.25	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
16:13:42.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:13:42.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:13:42.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:13:47.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:13:50.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:13:52.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:17:16.45	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of orbit
16:17:36.01	USH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 300ms.
16:17:39.56	USH	-	-	15	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 15ms.
16:17:44.80	USH	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 15ms to 75ms.

16:17:49.88	USH	-	-	-	250	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 250ms.
16:17:53.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:17:56.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:25:10.25	---	-	-	-	-	*** increase of orbit angle
16:25:29.02	---	-	-	-	-	*** to 25 deg
16:28:27.39	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of 25 deg orbit
16:28:45.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:28:46.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:28:46.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:28:48.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:28:54.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:28:56.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:35:07.37	SWS	-	-	-	250	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
16:35:15.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:35:23.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:40:03.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:40:03.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:40:03.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:40:06.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:40:11.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:40:14.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:40:23.41	LSH	-	-	-	990	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 990ms.
16:40:28.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:40:35.54	SWS	-	-	-	200	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
16:40:37.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:40:38.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:40:45.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:46:09.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:46:09.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:46:09.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:46:12.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:46:17.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:46:19.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:51:14.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:51:14.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:51:14.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:51:17.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:51:22.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:51:25.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:59:13.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:59:13.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:59:13.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:59:16.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:59:21.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:59:23.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:06:11.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:06:11.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:06:11.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:06:14.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:06:19.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:06:21.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:19:42.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:19:42.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:19:43.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:19:46.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:19:50.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:19:53.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:24:17.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:24:17.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:24:17.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:24:20.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:24:25.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:24:28.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

ARIES flight log

Flight: 3290

page 1 of

Date: 30/4/07

Operator(s): Joss

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: 1451 HOUSTON

EASTERN GULF OF MEXICO

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Fit ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
131130	Tranga	1/120	HBB	Clsd	7096	33.09	
133008	"	1/120	HBB	Clsd	7099	32.16	
132012	" "	1/60	Cal	Clsd	7034	28.14	
132207	" "	1/60	Cal	Clsd	7099	30.73	
132214	" "	600/1	Zen	open	7051	30.70	
132858	" "	1/60	Cal	Clsd	7091	30.65	
134030	" "	600/1	Nwd	Clsd	7090	31.09	
134559	P ₁	1/60	Cal	Clsd	7083	30.40	in Profile 1
14	P ₁			open			Profile ZHCNCHZ x 3. in Profile 1
141150	end P ₁	1/60	Cal	Clsd	7019	32.15	
141419		1/60	Cal	Clsd	7002	32.18	
141584	Start R1	1/60	Cal	Clsd	7082	32.37	
141651	R1	600/1	Nwd	Clsd	7105	32.73	100' 2141945 over ship water.
142258	R1	1/60	Cal	Clsd	7101	32.51	
142312	R1	120/1	Zen	open	7095	32.82	Clear above
142432	R1	480	Nwd	Clsd	7106	31.63	
142838	R1	1/60	Cal	Clsd	7081	32.62	
142955	R1	120/1	Zen	open	7065	32.14	Clear above
143107	R1	480/1	Nwd	Clsd	7071	33.05	
143509	R1	1/60	Cal	Clsd	7114	33.25	
143639	R1	120/1	Zen	open	7090	33.58	
143750	R1	480/1	Nwd	Clsd	7115	34.04	Stopped @ 144123
144137	R1 end	1/60	Cal	Clsd	7091	31.89	
150912	P2	1/60	Cal	Clsd	709	30.85	
151016	FL 2.1	420	Nwd	Clsd	7095	30.79	FL 2.80 end 151411
151424	end P2	1/60	Cal	Clsd	7097	30.49	
151714		1/60	Cal	Clsd	7061	30.66	
151840	R2.2	600/1	Nwd	Clsd	7081	30.78	
152335	" "	1/60	Cal	Clsd	7077	30.62	
152450	" "	120/1	Zen	open	7021	30.76	
152601	" "	480/1	Nwd	Clsd	7090	30.94	

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	30/04/07	Flight	B290	log pages
Operator(s)	Pollard	Campaign	JAIVEX			
Departure	Ellington	Arrival	Ellington			

**System start
MARSS**

Visual pod inspection						X
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						X
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						X
FERA on			at time	10:14:27		
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	26.6°C	Ch	26.2°C	Ch18	25.0°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on			at time	10:16:21		
Initial target temperatures	Hot	294.5	Cold	293.9		
Target heating						X
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						X
Scanning on (LMD box)			at time	10:20:05		
Scan indication		Monitor)		Visual	X

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software			at time			
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						
Scan indication		Monitor)		Visual	
Weather	Cloud		Precip			
	Surface		Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check (after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	11:57:38		
Brightness temps 'sensible'						X
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.45	Cold	295.40	
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold		
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	
	1	30.27	39.06	40.61	40.70	

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again					at time	

Flight:

B290

KEY

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nezvorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

Report Created 26/06/2007
15:39:01

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:
- DLUs:**
- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Last Updated:

08/05/2007

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:
- Aerosol**
- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B290

Date: 30 April 2007

Instruments

1. Not receiving SATCOM messages
2. Sondes – dropouts between 21kft and 15kft
3. DLU required resetting as lost data
4. Satcom phone still not working
5. 2DP 2DC not seeing cloud / unsure of problem
6. PCASP channel 1 problematic – possible channel 2
7. INU not aligned on return from New Orleans – probably FM finger trouble!

Aircraft

Nil

Satcom-H Calls

Not working

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B290:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP	No log appears to have been taken for this flight
Wet Nephelometer	No log appears to be available
FWVS	No log is taken for this FWVS
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	12 Nov 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Upward Facing Cameras
3 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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